

Active EMI Filter solution to enable a new electric aircraft paradigm.

1st Tania Cuesta Cano
Electrical systems
 Collins Aerospace ART-Ireland)
 Cork, Ireland
 tania.cuestacano@collins.com

2nd George Erotas
Electrical systems
 Collins Aerospace ART-Ireland
 Cork, Ireland
 george.erotas@collins.com

3th Douglas Pedroso
Electrical systems
 Collins Aerospace ART-Ireland
 Cork, Ireland
 douglasaraujo.pedroso@collins.com

4rd Ignacio Castro
Electrical systems
 Collins Aerospace ART-Ireland
 Cork, Ireland
 ignacio.castro@collins.com

Abstract—Achieving a light electrical power system is crucial for future aircraft electrification. Specific power is identified as one of the main enablers to prompt the new aviation paradigm. As a generic rule, EMI filters are expected to contribute from 20% to 40% of the power converter. Consequently, this is a main target on the weight optimization strategies. Active filter solutions are presented as a way of minimizing the EMI filter weight. This paper discusses on the main Active EMI filter (AEF) topologies and proposed a novel solutions to be implemented following a Hybrid EMI Filter (HEF) approach.

I. INTRODUCTION

EMI mitigation in the future electric aircraft presents serious challenges. This is due to the high voltage and power levels, the lack of scalability to this new scenario of the existed regulation and the high specific power requirements, while higher dv/dt and di/dt are expected. The weight constraint in a future electric aircraft imposes an extra layer of complexity. The weight optimization of passive EMI filters (PEFs) is mainly limited by the magnetic material technology that can be used for the filter inductor design, and subsequently the winding technique that can be utilized. In [1], an optimization method for filter inductors is investigated, which showed the limited degrees of optimization that PEFs have. In contrast, AEFs introduce additional design parameters that can be optimized, allowing for a larger design space [2].

Different AEF implementations have been evaluated by academia and industry as a solution to achieve further weight and volume reduction than the one reported by optimization algorithms [3]. There are two possible AEF implementations as shown in Figure 1. Figure 1.b shows a typical implementation where the AEF is installed and combined with a PEF [4], [5], and Figure 1.c represents a specific case where the AEF is used to modify the impedance

Fig. 1. Comparison of a PEF and two possible AEF implementations. a) Original PEF. b) AEF used in combination of a PEF. c) AEF particular used to active impedance modification.

of one element of the PEF, the shunt capacitance in the example exposed. This paper focuses on this specific case and in this document this approach is named as Hybrid EMI filter (HEF).

The paper is organized in the following manner: Section II covers the AEF state of the art, the main AEF topologies along with their implementation and characteristics. Section III focuses on the novel active solution proposed. Section IV offers experimental validation using a common mode (CM) T-Type filter. Section V summarises the main outcomes and conclusions of the work performed.

II. AEF STATE OF THE ART REVIEW

Active filtering gives numerous implementation options in terms of position, sensing and compensation. Therefore mapping all the possibilities can become complex. The review presented in [6]–[8] can be used as the starting point. In [6], [7], AEFs are classified based on the compensation signal used (i.e. voltage or current injection), on the sensing method (i.e. noise measured as voltage or current signal) and the compensation method (i.e. feedforward or feedback compensation). The analysis presented helps on the selection of the configuration as it is focused on defining requirements and limitations of each of the AEF configurations explained. Figure 2 illustrates all possible sensing-injection combinations that are covered. They are: current sensing-voltage compensation (CSVC), voltage sensing-voltage compensation (VSVC), voltage sensing-current compensation (VSCC) and current sensing-current compensation (CSCC). I_s and u_s refer to the current and voltage sensed signal, I_c and u_c are the current and voltage compensation signals.

Fig. 2. AEF types regarding measured and compensation signal. a) CSVC, b) VSVC, c) VSCC, d) CSCC

Depending on the compensation method, the noise mitigation nature of the filter is different. Voltage compensation will create a high impedance path in series with the noise source to attenuate the noise current. Therefore, it can be comparable to an inductor. On the other hand, current compensation creates a low impedance path in parallel with

the noise source, through where the current is recirculated. Thus, it would behave similarly to a capacitor.

Looking into how the noise measured is processed to generate the compensation signal, AEFs can be classified as feedback or feedforward compensation. In feedback compensation mode, the noise signal is measured at the receiver and the AEF output is generated by a close-loop response. In contrast, an AEF with feedforward compensation mode measures the noise at the source and generates a cancellation signal to mitigate the noise before reaching the receiver. Commonly, the sensing and injection signals share the same nature. From the cases displayed in Figure 2 only CSCC and VSVC AEF types can work in feedforward mode. Figure 3 illustrates CSCC and VSVC feedback, and forward versions. u_n and z_n are the noise voltage source and impedance, respectively. Z_{load} illustrates the load seen by the filter.

Fig. 3. VSVC and CSCC AEF configurations depending on the compensation method. a) CSCC feed-forward, b) CSCC feedback, c) VSVC feed-forward, d) VSVC feedback

Similarly to PEF, AEF filter performance can be evaluated based on insertion losses (IL). Analysing the IL expressions some operation particularities can be deduced which help on identifying the best application cases [6]. From the literature, it can be deduced that feedback method gives more flexibility in terms of design. The reason is that feedforward compensation requires deeper information of the system in order to guarantee unity gain and therefore a good attenuation. That can be translated into a higher dependency on component value accuracy.

The survey presented in [7] gives an extensive AEFs classification focusing in the implementation, covering the main three parts of the AEF: noise measurement, noise processing and compensation signal injection. Based on literature, the most common AEF solutions use current sensing and voltage injection, for instance [9]–[11]. However, in the case of a high power and high voltage power distribution system, the use of current transducers is challenging and should be avoided. One of the main two reasons is that those solutions tend to be more voluminous, costly and require higher cooling effort [12]. The second reason is scope based, as in this work the research has been oriented to AEF solutions to be implemented under

the scenario displayed in Figure 1(c), where, from the point of view of the author, voltage sensing solutions are more suitable. The capacitance coupling must be rated for the operating voltage and must be able to conduct the noise current, but not any of the operational (nominal) current allowing for the use of potentially light and small injection capacitors.

A. Hybrid EMI Filter conceptual design

The use of an AEF to modify the impedance of any element of a PEF is labelled as an HEF, see Figure 1 (c). The objective is to increase the attenuation of the original filter in a certain frequency range or to reach a similar response of the filter using smaller passive elements (i.e. to reduce the choke size). If the AEF acts as an active capacitor, the resultant HEF is labelled as Type I, and if the AEF acts as an inductor instead, it is a HEF Type II. Figure 4 illustrates the mentioned cases. Active capacitors are usually implemented with current compensation AEFs and active inductors with voltage compensation AEFs.

Fig. 4. HEF used with or in PEF. a) PEF and AEF cascaded, b) HEF Type I, c) HEF Type II and d) Symbology Legend

In this work HEF type II is explored. This HEF type is especially interesting for bypassing the shunt capacitance limitation imposed by specific industry safety standards relating to lightning strikes. The conceptual idea is that a passive capacitor can be designed to be under the maximum allowed capacitance defined by the lightning strike regulations meanwhile the AEF is working as an active capacitor, virtually increasing the effective capacitance along a certain frequency range. Therefore, the size of the entire filter can be reduced, as for the same attenuation the required inductance can be reduced. Furthermore, the safety requirements regarding lightning strike can be guaranteed, as the AEF can be disconnected in case of a lightning strike, leaving only the passive capacitance in operation. For a feedforward system, the identification of source and load impedances is a strict requirement to guarantee performance and stability. However, as aircraft propulsion systems are complex, these parameters are hard to identify. As such, feedback compensation is preferred. The design of a HEF can follow the same passive

EMI filter design methodology. Where the AEF is seen in the HEF as an active admittance defined by the compensating current, I_c , and the noise voltage, u_s , it is Y_{VSCC} .

The influence of the AEF in the original PEF IL characteristic is studied. The IL of the most common PEF topologies converted to HEF are displayed in Table I. Where, Z_{lisen} is the impedance of the line impedance stabilization network (LISN) and Z_{lcm} the common mode choke (CMC) impedance. Ideally, the active VSCC AEF will act as a shunt path at the selected actuation frequency range. This is expressed as an admittance, Y_{VSCC} , and replace the original term related to the capacitor impedance ($1/Z_c$) in the IL equations. The aim of the AEF is to emulate the behaviour of an equivalent passive capacitor along the actuation frequency range. Increasing Y_{VSCC} , it can be seen that the IL will increase by analysing the equation.

TABLE I
MAIN FILTER TYPE IL EXPRESSION

Filter Type	IL
Inverse Gamma	$IL_{IG} = 1 + \frac{Z_{lcm}}{Z_{lisen} + Z_n} + Y_{VSCC} \cdot \frac{Z_n \cdot (Z_{lcm} + Z_{lisen})}{Z_{lisen} + Z_n}$
Gamma	$IL_G = 1 + \frac{Z_{lcm}}{Z_{lisen} + Z_n} + Y_{VSCC} \cdot \frac{Z_{lisen} \cdot (Z_{lcm} + Z_n)}{Z_{lisen} + Z_n}$
T-type	$IL_T = 1 + \frac{2 \cdot Z_{lcm}}{Z_{lisen} + Z_n} + Y_{VSCC} \cdot \frac{(Z_{lcm} + Z_{lisen}) \cdot (Z_{lcm} + Z_n)}{Z_{lisen} + Z_n}$

The the analysis presented in this work proposes two novel VSCC AEF solutions as a contribution to the state of the art [13]. The actuation frequency range targeted in the context of this work is from 150 kHz to 10 MHz. Further explanation is provided in the following section.

III. ACTIVE EMI MITIGATION SOLUTION

In this section a novel AEF solution based on voltage feedback (VFB) operational amplifiers (OPAs), which enable shunt capacitor impedance modification along the actuation frequency range of any EMI filter is presented. The non-ideal characteristics of the analog elements used are taken into account, analysing their influence over the desired frequency response of the circuitry. Compensation techniques are included in order to minimize their impact. The design is able to emulate the impedance behaviour of a capacitor up to 10 MHz. In the following lines, the theoretical analysis and design are explained.

To develop the AEF based on OPAs a wide-band frequency operation capability is needed. This is one of the reasons some literature has proposed current-fed (CFB) OPA based solutions [14]–[16]. Even though the constant bandwidth feature makes CFB OPA attractive, the close-loop bandwidth is determined by an internal capacitor and the external feedback resistor. This means the latest must be fixed for optimum stability, while any stray capacitance across the feedback will cause instability. Consequently, the degree of freedom in the design is reduced. This is the main reason why the design presented here is based purely in VFB OPAs. The approach introduced here has mainly three different stages, Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Scheme of the AEF configuration with a shaping and a decoupling stage.

A. Shaping stage

The aim of the VSCC active element is to control the injected current based on the input voltage measurement so the lumped behaviour is that of a shunt capacitor. The admittance of the system displayed in Figure 5 should be equal to the one of an equivalent capacitor of value C_{eq} . It is,

$$Y_{VSCC} = \frac{I_c}{u_s} = C_{eq} \cdot s. \quad (1)$$

Where, s is the Laplace operator.

The study of the system is oriented to impedance analysis. The shaping stage is focused on obtaining the desired impedance over the frequency response of interest. This stage is implemented with an inverting OPA configuration where Z_i and Z_f define the inverting gain of the OPA while the injection branch can be seen as a load. The analysis of the input admittance of the filter yields

$$Y_{VSCC}^A = \frac{R_c + R_i \cdot G_1}{R_i \cdot R_c} \cdot s \cdot \frac{s + \frac{1 + C_c/C_i \cdot G_1}{C_c \cdot (R_c + R_i \cdot G_1)}}{(s + \frac{1}{C_i \cdot R_i})(s + \frac{1}{C_c \cdot R_c})}, \quad (2)$$

where G_1 is

$$G_1 = \frac{C_i \cdot (s \cdot C_f \cdot R_f + 1)}{C_f \cdot (s \cdot C_i \cdot R_1 + 1)}, \quad (3)$$

and Z_i , Z_f and Z_c are the input, the feedback and in injection impedances. They are defined as a RC series branch and their elements labelled as C_x and R_x , where “x” it’s a subscript placeholder.

An initial design requirement is set for the feedback impedance. It is desired for G_1 to remain constant for all frequencies. Therefore,

$$C_f \cdot R_f = C_i \cdot R_i \quad (4)$$

Once this is applied, the rest of elements can be designed to keep a capacitive admittance behaviour along all the frequency range of interest. The applied methodology was based on locating the poles defined by the Z_i and Z_c branches out of

the actuation frequency range (i.e at frequencies higher than 10 MHz). In Figure 6 it can be seen how by appropriately selecting the impedances, the active element admittance would behave as a capacitance among the full frequency range (Design B).

Fig. 6. Admittance frequency response of the active system.

B. Boosting stage

Although the capacitance could be increased by increasing the gain G_1 , it is preferable to add an additional stage to boost it.

A straightforward way of implement the boosting stage is to use a non-inverting OPA to increase the gain by connected it to the output of the first stage. The impedance equation (2) and capacitor value does not change but the term G_1 will turn into G'_1 ,

$$G'_1 = \left(1 + \frac{Z_f}{Z_i} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{R_2}{R_1}\right)\right). \quad (5)$$

In a practical implementation the attenuation of high frequency noise is needed to avoid oscillations in the AEF. The parasitic capacitance of the CMC becomes dominant at a certain frequency, bypassing the inductor and resulting in a loss of attenuation. The active system can amplify any non-desired noise component, thus a recommended design practice is to implement a low pass filter in the AEF loop to avoid noise components above the cut-off frequency from harming the AEF operation. A Sallen-Key filter is recommended to provide gain amplification and high frequency attenuation.

C. Decoupling stage

Theoretically, this last stage is not needed. Nonetheless, there are non-ideal properties of OPAs which need to be considered to achieve proper performance of the AEF.

OPA devices have inherent output resistance (R_o). If a capacitive load, C_L , is connected to the output, the stability of the system is penalised. This happens because R_o in conjunction with the capacitance form an additional pole in the amplifier

loop gain transfer function. The additional pole could be placed at frequencies lower than the GBP, which contributes with -20 dB/dec and 90 lag. The stability of the OPA can be studied based on the open loop gain ($A\beta$). For both the non-inverting and inverting OPA configuration $A\beta$ is defined by equation,

$$A\beta = \frac{K}{(s + \tau_1) \cdot (s + \tau_2)} \cdot \frac{Z_i}{Z_f + Z_i} \cdot \frac{1}{R_o \cdot C_L \cdot s + 1} \quad (6)$$

Where K is the DC OPA gain and τ_1 and τ_2 internal OPAs loop gain poles.

The decoupling stage consists of an OPA working as a buffer to provide a high impedance at the output of the second stage. Choosing an OPA with a high capacitance loading capability will help the system to decouple the injection branch from the previous stages without introducing modifications on the admittance definition. The influence of the decoupling stage has been verified in simulation using the SPICE model of a real OPA (i.e. macromodel, Figure 7. The high frequency peak around 40 MHz is due to first stage internal resonances.

Fig. 7. Admittance frequency response of a spice model without decoupling stage (blue) and with decoupling stage (red).

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

This section presents the experimental validation results of a T-Type HEF. The HEF filter response has been verified with a Vector Network Analyser (VNA) and compared with an equivalent passive solution. Figure 8 illustrates the prototype developed and Figure 9 illustrates the frequency response.

During the experimental validation, it was observed that designs with low injection impedance have a noisy response during feedback operation. A solution is to design the AEF so the impedance of the injection branch is high enough to avoid the high frequency looping phenomena. The main drawback is this solution decreases the achievable frequency response range.

After validating the impedance behaviour of the active solution, the AEF has been incorporated in a common-mode EMI filter. The scheme of the HEF under study is represented

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. Prototype photo. (a) Top view. (b)Bottom view.

Fig. 9. Frequency response of the solution and the equivalent passive capacitor

in Figure 10, the common-mode T-type filter prototype is shown in Figure 11.

The attenuation response of the HEF is compared with an equivalent passive solution, a PEF with identical passive capacitance than the one generated actively (i.e. 300 nF). The frequency response of the two cases are displayed in Figure 12. An additional case with the active filter disconnected has been also evaluated, labelled as “original”. Thus it can be seen what it would be the HEF response if the AEF should be shut-down because of light strike protection reasons.

As it can be seen the HEF insertion loss is of the same

Fig. 10. CM filter configuration of the HEF prototype

Fig. 11. CM T-type prototype.

Fig. 12. T-Type filter frequency response of the HEF and the PEF with equivalent passive capacitance.

order as the passive filter but with a reduced cut-off frequency, showing that the AEF only affects the shunt path and not the fundamental topology of the filter. It should be noted that the performance of the AEF at frequencies near 1 MHz is limited by the ground impedance, in a manner similar to that of a passive capacitor as the sensed noise voltage will start being unequal to the actual common-mode voltage after the resonance of the active capacitor and ground inductance [22].

V. CONCLUSIONS

Active EMI mitigation solutions show potential for reduced size and weight over traditional PEFs. Two active solutions,

based on VSCC AEF configuration, have been proposed for being implemented in a HEF. The aim of the design methods presented consists on the replication of the behaviour of a passive shunt capacitor.

The approach proposed is an analog electronics circuit based on VFB OPAs. It has demonstrated the active amplification capability of the C_y capacitance of a CM filter up to 10 MHz. A study case, in which the C_y is amplified nearly 10 times has been successfully validated. Limitations on the maximum compensation current and EMI voltage magnitude processing capabilities have been detected. A solution to overcome the maximum compensation current constrains could be to use a LPA.

Weight and volume comparison of the AEF prototype with an equivalent passive capacitor have been compared. The active solution achieves lower volume and weight than the equivalent passive capacitor solution, with the active circuit having a volume and weight of 2.8 cm^3 and 20g respectively. The resulting decrease in the required common-mode inductance was not quantified, but smaller cores with reduced number of turns could be used additionally decreasing the size of the total filter. Lastly, the PCB integration capability of the AEF is an additional benefit over passive capacitors.

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